

Semi-automated DNA extraction from leaf and seed tissue of wheat using a liquid handling station and magnetic beads

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INTRODUCTION

High-throughput genotyping as a tool to assist the genetic improvement of wheat and other crops requires automated and reliable methods for DNA extraction with appropriate quality. Examples of today commonly used SNP technologies adopted in crop breeding programs are the 'Kompetitive Allele Specific PCR (KASP)' or 'genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS)' platforms, which allow the genotyping of hundreds to thousands of individuals. Automated equipment such as liquid handling stations, can complete DNA extractions for a greater number of samples, in less time and at a lower cost compared to manual processing. To achieve adequate DNA quality and satisfy downstream application needs, separating the soluble DNA from cell debris and other insoluble materials is vital and should not be underestimated. Several DNA extraction chemistries are available and follow the four main steps of DNA extraction, which are the lysis, separation of the soluble DNA by binding to a purification matrix, washing proteins and other contaminants away and elution of the DNA. The ability to extract DNA of different parts of the crop, regardless of the phenological stage in the crop cycle and conditioned to the requirements of plant breeding (Dreisigacker et al. 2016) denotes great advantage, for example, presenting genotyping results before planting or making new crosses in the field or greenhouse for the next breeding cycle.

The protocol presented here, was established in the Wheat Molecular Breeding Laboratory of CIMMYT's Global Wheat Program in the framework of the USAID funded 'Feed the Future Innovation Lab for Applied Wheat Genomics'. The DNA extraction method makes use of a Beckman Biomek i7 liquid handling station and the magnetic particle-based 'Sbeadex mini plant extraction kit' (Biosearch Technologies). This protocol was developed using green leaf tissue or seed of hexaploid bread wheat. The protocol is divided into four sections: A) Sample preparation; B) DNA extraction using the Sbeadex mini plant extraction kit; C) Programming of the liquid handling station; and D) DNA quantification.

A. SAMPLE PREPARATION

Leaf tissue

1. Prepare 96-well plates (Onetip Product no. E1760) for sampling the leaf tissue. A plate layout must be generated depending on the specifications of genotyping, which includes the arrangement and label of the samples (Figure 1). It is important that each sample is identified and corresponds to the individual plant or plot in the field or greenhouse.

PT21GSBM-B01		INTERTEK-CB-SATYN-WCYT											
PT21GSBM	WSD1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	CB RECURRENT PARENTS Y20-21 1	9	17	CB PARTITIONING WCYT Y21 1	6	4	12	19	27	8	3	10	
B	2	10	18	2	7	5	13	20	CB SOURCE SINK WCYT Y20-21 1	9	4	11	
C	3	11	19	3	8	6	14	21	2	10	5	12	
D	4	12	20	CB BEST PTXPT WCYT Y20-21 1	9	7	15	22	3	11	6	13	
E	5	13	21	2	10	8	16	23	4	12	7	14	
F	6	14	22	3	CB BIOMASS WCYT Y20-21 1	9	17	24	5	13	8	CB WCYT Y20-21 1	
G	7	15	CB ROOTS SATYN DROUGHT Y21 1	4	2	10	18	25	6	CB WHEAT CAP Y20-21 1	9	2	
H	8	16	2	5	3	11		26	7	2			

Figure 1. Example of 96-well plate layout. The red cell indicates a random empty well unique for each plate. The blue cells are kept empty to place specific controls. The black cells indicate a set of new genetic materials.

2. Each 96-well plate must also be labeled. For example, at CIMMYT plate labels include: the name of breeding program, the year, the purpose the genetic material to be genotyped, the name of the scientist requesting the genotyping, the name of the genetic material, start-end number of the sample batch and the sampling date. The extraction plates contain 12 strips of 8 microtubes of 1.1 ml (Onetip Product no. E1730).
3. Sampling of green leaf tissue can be carried out in the field or in the greenhouse. Cut 4 pieces of green leaf of 1 x 1 cm size, and place them inside the 1.1 ml microtubes, to obtain approximately between 5 and 10 mg of tissue.
4. After sampling of each 96-well plate in the field or greenhouse, as well as during transportation to the laboratory, seal the plates carefully and place them in a cooler with ice to avoid dehydration and tissue damage.
5. Transfer the plates as soon as possible in a -80 °C freezer (Thermo Scientific, Mod. 3767A) for a minimum of 3 to 4 hours.

6. Subsequently, locate the unsealed plates into a freeze dryer (Labconco, Mod. 7754041) taking care that the temperature is maintained at -50 °C and the vacuum levels kept at 0.00 - 0.12 mBars. For 1 to 4 96-well plates, a period of 24 hours of lyophilization is required, for 5 to 15 plates between 48 to 72 hours.
7. Add a stainless-steel bead (4 mm, JEB) inside each microtube using a 5 mm bead dispenser (Quiagen, Mod. 69975) and seal the plates well with their respective caps (Thermo Scientific, Product no. AB-0784).
8. Transfer the plates into a tissue homogenizer (GenoGrinder2010, Zymo Research) and grind the tissue for 2-3 minutes at 1750 rpm until fine powder is obtained.
9. To remove the beads, take each strip of 1.1ml microtubes in the 96-well plates and incline. Seal the plates and keep them in the fridge until DNA extraction.

Seed tissue

10. Prepare 96-well plates (Onetip Product no. E1760) for sampling the leaf tissue. A plate layout must be generated depending on the specifications of genotyping, which includes the arrangement and label of the samples (Figure 1). It is important that each sample is identified and corresponds to the individual plant or plot in the field or greenhouse.
11. Each 96-well plate must also be labeled. For example, at CIMMYT plate labels include: the name of breeding program, the year, the purpose the genetic material to be genotyped, the name of the scientist requesting the genotyping, the name of the genetic material, start-end number of the sample batch and the sampling date. The extraction plates contain 12 strips of 8 microtubes of 1.1 ml (Onetip Product no. E1730).
 1. Place one seed from each sample in the 1.1 ml microtubes according to the plate layout.
 2. Add 200ul of ddH₂O to each microtube.
 3. Locate the 96-well plates into a fume hood (Labconco, Mod. 6963601) and soak the seed in ddH₂O for 2 days at room temperature. The soaking allows the seed to take a soft consistency.
 4. Seal the plates and place them in a -80°C freezer (Thermo Scientific, Mod. 3767A) for a minimum of 3 to 4 hours.
 5. Subsequently, transfer the unsealed plates, but covered with some tissue to prevent their escape into a freeze dryer (Labconco, Mod. 7754041) taking care that the temperature is maintained at -50 °C and the vacuum levels kept at 0.00 - 0.12 mBars for a minimum of 3 days.

6. Add a stainless-steel bead (4 mm, JEB) inside each microtube using a 5 mm bead dispenser (Quiagen, Mod. 69975) and seal the plates well with their respective caps (Thermo Scientific, Product no. AB-0784).
7. Transfer the plates into a tissue homogenizer (GenoGrinder2010, Zymo Research) and grind the tissue for 2-3 minutes at 1750 rpm until fine powder is obtained. Verify that the flour is finely ground and eventually repeat grinding. In a few cases the seed tissue might need to be loosen up using an Allen 7/32 key before second grinding.
8. To remove the beads after grinding, take each strip of 1.1ml microtubes in the 96-well plates and incline. Seal the plates and keep them in the fridge until DNA extraction.

B. DNA EXTRACTION USING THE SBEADEx MINI PLANT EXTRACTION KIT (BIOSEARCH TECHNOLOGIES)

The 'sbeadex[®] mini plant kit' (Product no. 41610) has been developed by LGC Biosearch Technologies (<https://www.biosearchtech.com/>) and is based on magnetic particles (beads) capable to specifically bind nucleic acids such as DNA and separate it from the cell debris and other materials. The use of magnetic plates in the setup of the liquid handler station supports the formation of ring type structures of the magnetic beads at the bottom of each tube. This way washings collect and discard the residues from the tissue samples.

Lysis

The lysis is prepared manually in a fume hood (Labconco, Mod. 110810000), following the next six steps:

1. Add 150 μ l of 'lysis buffer PN' and 15 μ l of RNase (Sigma, Product no. R4875) into each microtube that contains a tissue sample. Seal the plates with their respective caps.
2. Place a silicone cap (Corning, Product no. 3090) and a polystyrene plate (Corning, Product no. 3795) on the sample plates and clasp around some thick rubber band to have a tight sealing. Tap on the plates for 1 minute to ensure all tissue in the tubes gets moisturized.
3. Before incubation, verify again that the grinded tissue is completely moistened for lysis.
4. Put the plates into a portable mixer (Fisher Scientific, Mod. 14-59-346) which can be placed into an incubator (DyCe LAB, Salvis LAB, Mod. Ic 400) and shake for 30 minutes at 65 °C.
5. Remove the plates from the incubator, remove the rubber band, polystyrene plate, and the silicone sealing cap from the plates.

6. Centrifuge the plates for 20 minutes at 3750 rpm at 22 °C (Beckman coulter, Mod. Allegra X-12R). Remove and unseal the plates for transfer to the liquid handling station.

C. LIQUID HANDLING STATION: BECKMAN BIOMEK I7

The Biomek i7 liquid handling station (Beckman Coulter, Mod. B87581) (Figure 2) (<https://www.beckman.mx/liquid-handlers/biomek-i7>) is spacious and has up to 45 automated labware positioners (ALP). For sample processing in this protocol, the equipment must have four additional devices: (1) a plate stirrer with speed and temperature control (HV1), (2) a plate shaker (Peltier1), (3) magnetic plates and (4) a washing station. We optimized this protocol using an equipment with a single arm and a 96-channel head with the capacity to pipette 1030 µl (Pod1). Further a flexible gripper (Gripper) is required that transports the plates to the different ALP. The equipment runs with the software 'Biomek Software V5.0' (<https://www.beckman.com/liquid-handlers/software/biomek/b87468>) which is quite easy to manipulate and program. The software guide all operations.

Figure 2. Biomek i7

Binding[®], Washing (Wash1, Wash2) and Elution[®] for extraction of 9 DNA plates

Preparation of the Biomek equipment

It is recommended to set up the equipment during lysis. The following steps described are specific to the Biomek i7 series. It must be considered that for proper handling of the equipment, training on operations and programming should have been provided previously by the vendor. This protocol is set up for the simultaneous DNA extraction of 9 microtiter plates.

Startup steps:

1. Turn on the equipment and its light.
2. Turn on the HV1 that as it regulates the temperature of Peltier1.
3. The washing station must have deionized (DI) water for example from a Milli-Q (Millipore, Mod. Reference). 35 liters of water are sufficient for washing tips during DNA extraction of this 9-plate protocol.
4. Place an empty gallon to collect the liquid waste with the necessary capacity (approximately 35 liters of water).
5. Turn on the computer and open the Biomek V5.0 software.
6. Place Pod1 and the gripper in the 'Home All Axes' position to make the PC-Biomek connection.
7. Activate the Masterflex®L/S® wash pump (Cole-Parmer, Mod. 77200-52) to verify that each channel of the washing station carries enough water, if necessary, use a clean 1/4" swab to remove residues that have remained from past extractions. At the end of this step deactivate the pump.
8. According to the number of plates used for DNA extraction, 9 plates in this case, a total 44 ALP on the deck of the equipment will be used following the 'Guided setup' (Figure 3). Place all necessary materials (Labware) on each of its assigned positions (ALP).
9. Add the 'Sbeadex' chemistries into their respective reservoirs: 'Binding buffer', 'Wash1' and 'Wash2'. The 'Sbeadex' and 'Elution' solutions will be added when required and the equipment will pause, both steps have been programmed in the software.

2. It's suggested to keep hands outside the work area of the equipment once the protocol has started. The equipment will stop the protocol automatically due to the activation of sensors detecting any movement.

3. **Binding:** The equipment first transfers for all plates. The tips are then washed at the washing station (Figure 4).

<p><u>Aspir</u> 120µl</p>	<p><i>Pipetting technique:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aspir_Binding_1000µl <p><i>Pipetting template:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Binding dispense <p><i>Deep:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1mm from bottom 	<p>Tip Handling</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Load <u>tips2</u> tips and <u>leave them on</u> when the transfer is done.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Wash tips in <u>Water</u> : 4 cycles of 110% %</p> <p>Use the technique: <input type="checkbox"/> Auto-Select <input type="button" value="Customize..."/> <input type="button" value="Save As..."/></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Change tips between sources. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Change tips between destinations.</p>
<p><u>Dispen</u> 120µl</p> <p>Draw Binding from Binding using the Aspir_Binding_1000ul technique.</p> <p>1.00 mm from bottom</p>		
<p><u>Wash</u> tips</p>	<p><i>Pipetting technique:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Washing wash tips <p><i>Pipetting template:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> washing wash <p><i>Deep:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2mm from liquid at 100µl/s 2mm from liquid at 75µl/s 	<p>Destination: Extraccion1</p> <p>Dispense 120 µL of Binding to Extraccion1 using the Dispen_Binding_1000ul technique.</p> <p>3.00 mm from liquid</p>

Figure 4. Pipetting technique for 'Binding'

4. **Sbeadex:** The equipment pauses to be able to add the 'Sbeadex' solution (magnetic beads) into its reservoir. This solution must be well mixed (taking care that no sediment remains in the original bottle). The equipment will perform a multi-dispense of 10 µl of 'Sbeadex' from its reservoir to each extraction plate, using the BC1070µl tips. The 'Binding' and 'Sbeadex' solution in each extraction plate is subsequently mixed twice with the Peltier1. Washing the tips is again performed at the end of dispensing (Figure 5).

<p><u>Aspir</u> <u>50μl</u></p> <p>Labware Type: SBSDeep96Square Pod: Pod1 Position: Extraccion1 <input type="checkbox"/> Empty Tips Liquid Type: Sbeadex Volume: 10 μL</p>		
<p><u>Dispen</u> <u>10μl</u></p> <p>Dispense</p>	<p><i>Pipetting technique:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dispen_Sbeadex_1000μl <p><i>Pipetting template:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sbeadex <p><i>Deep:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1mm from bottom 	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Auto-Select Customize... Save As...</p> <p>Technique: Dispen_Sbeadex_1000μl</p>
<p><u>Wash</u> <u>tips</u></p>	<p><i>Pipetting technique:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Washing wash tips <p><i>Pipetting template:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> washing wash tips <p><i>Deep:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2mm from liquid at 100μl/s 2mm from liquid at 75μl/s 	<p>Labware Type: BCUpsideDownTipBoxLid Pod: Pod1 Position: Sbeadex <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Refresh Tips tips2 Liquid Type: Well Contents Volume: 50 μL</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Auto-Select Customize... Save As...</p> <p>Technique: Aspir_Sbeadex_1000μl_Mezclado</p>

Figure 5. Pipetting technique for 'Sbeadex'

5. **Shaking:** Mixing of plates using the Peltier1. The Peltier1 is activated, indicating 'start shaking' at a speed of 2000 rpm diagonally (NW to SE) for 15 seconds (Figure 6).

Using the device at position Peltier1

Start Shaking

Shake at 2000 RPM (Approximately 100-2000 based on plate weight)

Use one shake style Alternate between two shake styles

Shake using Diagonal (NW to SE)

Figure 6. Parameters for mixing with Peltier1.

6. The equipment pauses once more for adding the tissue plates, centrifuged after the initial lysis. A total of 90 μl of lysis will be transferred into the extraction plates, which contain the mix of 'Binding buffer' and 'Sbeadex' solution using the BC230 μl tips (Figure 7). Each extraction plate has its box of 230 μl tips individually assigned to avoid any contamination between samples. Using the Gripper, each extraction plates are taken to the Peltier1 where mixing is performed twice (Figure 6). After mixing plates are returned to their ALP, where static incubation for 240 seconds is accomplished.

<u>Aspir</u> 90μl <p>2.00 mm from bottom</p> </div>		
<u>Dispen</u> 90μl Dispense	Pipetting technique: • DISPEN_LISIS 230TIPS Pipetting template: • Lysis Deep: • 2mm from bottom	
<u>Wash tips</u>	Pipetting technique: • Washing wash tips Pipetting template: • washing wash Deep: • 2mm from liquid at 100 $\mu\text{l}/\text{s}$ • 2mm from liquid at 75 $\mu\text{l}/\text{s}$	

Figure 7. Pipetting technique for 'Lysis'

7. **Purification:** After incubation, the extraction plates are transferred to the magnetic plates for 60 seconds. The magnetic beads attach to the bottom of each tube and form a type of ring which allows to remove 250 μl of the binding + sbeadex + lysis waste for purification. The waste is unloaded in the wash station using the BC1070 μl tips. The plates are returned to their original ALP (Figure 8). Tip washing is performed at the end of dispensing the waste from each plate.

<u>Aspir Well contents</u> 250µl	<i>Pipetting technique:</i> • Aspir_desechos_230µl <i>Pipetting template:</i> • Lysis template <i>Deep:</i> • 0 mm from bottom
<u>Dispen Tips Contents</u> 250µl	<i>Pipetting technique:</i> • Dispen_Desechos_230µl <i>Pipetting template:</i> • desechos dispense <i>Deep:</i> • 2 mm from liquid
<u>Wash tips</u>	<i>Pipetting technique:</i> • Washing wash tips <i>Pipetting template:</i> • washing wash <i>Deep:</i> • 2mm from liquid at 100µl/s • 2mm from liquid at 75µl/s

Tip Handling

Load tips2 tips and leave them on when the transfer is done.

Wash tips in Water : 4 cycles of 110% %

Use the technique: Auto-Select Customize... Save As...

Change tips between sources. Change tips between destinations.

Source: Extraccion1

0.00 mm from bottom

Draw **Well Contents** from **Extraccion1** using the **Aspir_desechos_230ul** technique.

Destination: WS1

20.00 mm from bottom

Dispense **250 µL** of **Wash1** to **WS1** using the **Dispen_Desechos_230ul** technique.

Figure 8. Pipetting technique for 'Waste'.

Note: The DNA extraction protocol uses buffers (solutions) that maybe toxic and harmful to health.

8. Wash 1.

The equipment performs a multi-dispense of 200 µl of Wash1 (Table 1 and 2) with the BC1070µl tips. Plates are subsequently mixed 2 times using the Peltier1. Tip washing is performed at the end of dispensing (Figure 9).

Table 1. WASH 1 76% EtOH, 0.2 M NaOA

STOCK	100 ml	300 ml	500 ml
EtOH ¹ Absoluta	76 ml	228 ml	380 ml
2.5 M NaOAc ^{Table2}	8 ml	24 ml	40 ml
dH ₂ O	16 ml	48 ml	80 ml

¹ Absolute Ethanol (Merck 100983).

Table 2. 2.5 M NaOAc

Dissolve 20.5 g sodium acetate¹ (anhydride, MW=82.03) in dH₂O to a final volume of 100 ml. Autoclave.

¹ Sodium acetate trihydrate 1kg (Sigma S-9513).

<p><u>Aspir</u> 800µl</p>		
<p><u>Dispen</u> 200µl</p>		
<p><u>Wash tips</u></p>	<p><i>Pipetting technique:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Washing wash tips <p><i>Pipetting template:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • washing wash <p><i>Deep:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2mm from liquid at 100µl/s • 2mm from liquid at 75µl/s 	<p>Labware Type: BCUpsideDownTipBoxLid Pod: Pod1</p> <p>Position: Wash1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Refresh Tips tips2</p> <p>Liquid Type: Wash1</p> <p>Volume: 800 µL</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Auto-Select Customize... Save As...</p> <p>Technique: Aspir tips_1000WASH1</p>

Figure 9. Pipetting technique for 'WASH 1'.

9. The plates are again transferred to the magnetic plates for 60 seconds to be able to remove 250 µl of Wash 1 waste that is unloaded in the washing station using the BC1070µl tips. The plates are returned to their original ALP (Figure 8).

10. **Wash 2.**

The equipment will perform a multi-dispense of 200 µl of Wash2 (Table 3) with the BC1070µl tips. Plates are mixed 2 times using the Peltier1. The tips are washed at the end of dispensing (Figure 10).

Table 3. WASH 2 76% EtOH, 10 mM NH₄OAc

STOCK	100 ml	300 ml	500 ml
EtOH ¹ Absoluta	76 ml	228 ml	380 ml
1 M NH ₄ OAc ^{Table4}	1 ml	3 ml	5 ml
dH ₂ O	23 ml	69 ml	115 ml

¹ Absolute Ethanol (Merck 100983).

Table 4. 1 M NH₄OAc

Dissolve 7.71 g ammonium acetate¹ (MW=77.08) in dH₂O to a final volume of 100 ml. Filtered out.

¹ NH₄OAc (Sigma A1542-500G).

<p><u>Aspir</u> 800µl</p>		
<p><u>Dispen</u> 200µl</p>	<p><i>Pipetting technique:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Dispen_tips1000WASH2 <p><i>Pipetting template:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Wash SMZ <p><i>Deep:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 10mm from bottom	<p>Labware Type: SBSDeep96Square Pod: Pod1 Position: Extraccion1 <input type="checkbox"/> Empty Tips Liquid Type: Wash2 Volume: 200 µL</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Auto-Select Customize... Save As...</p> <p>Technique: Dispen_tips1000WASH2</p>
<p><u>Wash tips</u></p>	<p><i>Pipetting technique:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Washing wash tips <p><i>Pipetting template:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• washing wash <p><i>Deep:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 2mm from liquid at 100µl/s• 2mm from liquid at 75µl/s	<p>Labware Type: BCUpsideDownTipBoxLid Pod: Pod1 Position: Wash2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Refresh Tips tips2 Liquid Type: Wash2 Volume: 800 µL</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Auto-Select Customize... Save As...</p> <p>Technique: Aspir_tips 1000WASH2</p>

Figure 10. Pipetting technique for 'WASH 2'.

11. The plates are transferred to the magnetic plates for 60 seconds to be able to remove 250 µl of Wash 2 waste that is unloaded in the washing station using the BC1070µl tips. The plates are returned to their original ALP (Figure 8).
12. **Elution:** The equipment will pause to manually add the 'elution' solution which should be pre-heated to a temperature of 65 °C resulting in better yields of DNA. The 'elution' will break the binding between the magnetic beads and the DNA. A total of 70 µl of the 'elution' solution will be dispensed into each plate using the BC1070µl tips. Plates are mixed twice in the Peltier1. The plates incubate 360 seconds inside the 'deck' at room temperature (Figure 11).

<p><u>Aspir</u> 60µl</p> <p>Aspirate</p>	<p><i>Pipetting technique:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aspir_DNA_230µlTips <p><i>Pipetting template:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DNA Aspir <p><i>Deep:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0.5mm from bottom
<p><u>Dispen</u> 60µl</p> <p>Dispense</p>	<p><i>Pipetting technique:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dispen_DNA_230µl <p><i>Pipetting template:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DNA dispense <p><i>Deep:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2mm from bottom

Tip Handling

Load 1 tips and unload them when the transfer is done.

Wash tips in Water : 4 cycles of 110% %

Use the technique: Auto-Select Customize... Save As...

Change tips between sources. Change tips between destinations.

Source: Extraccion1

0.50 mm from bottom

Draw DNA from Extraccion1 using the Aspir_DNA_230ulTips technique.

Destination: DNA1

2.00 mm from bottom

Dispense 60 µL of DNA to DNA1 using the Dispen_DNA_230ul technique.

Figure 12. Pipetting technique for 'DNA'.

D. CUANTIFICACIÓN DE ADN

After extraction, DNA quantification should be performed, for example using spectrometry (ThermoScientific, Mod. NanoDrop Eight) or running an agarose gel (Figure 13 and 14). The average concentration of DNA obtained with the described protocol is around 100-120 ng/µl for leaf tissue, with DNA quality parameters of approximately 1.4 for the absorbance ratio 260/280 and 1.7 for the ratio 260/230. The average DNA concentration using seed tissue is around 150-180 ng/µl with a 260/280 absorbance ratio of approximately 1.7 and a 260/230 absorbance ratio of 1.0. DNA of both tissue types have successfully been used for genotyping for KASP and GBS genotyping

Figure 13. Quantification in NanoDrop Eight.

Figure 14. Agarose quality gel.

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